

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE LEVEL AND PATIENT TREATMENT IN DENTAL CLINICS OF TBILISI

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Abstract

The aim of our study is to assess the level of patient knowledge regarding the procedures and treatment methods that are performed and will be performed in dental clinics in Tbilisi.

The material was collected through questionnaires prepared by us. The questionnaire consisted of two parts: the first part was demographic, and the second part was specific.

The individuals participating in the study were randomly selected in dental clinics in Tbilisi.

The statistical processing of the material was conducted using the statistical program SPSS.

Keywords: level of knowledge, non-stationary clinic, random, preventive examination, treatment procedure.

Introduction

In recent years, significant changes have been made to improve the quality of dental care for patients. The material - technical base of dental treatment - prophylactic facilities has been upgraded.

Nowadays, both state and private dental facilities offer dental care to patients. The differences between them are clearly evident in the quality and level of dental care. Consequently, during treatment, a stomatologist has a greater advantage if they are well-acquainted with their patient as a recipient of dental services. So far, as is known, stomatologists have been unable to answer crucial questions: who constitutes the dental practice patient? What psychological and ethical-legal status does the patient possess? The aesthetic status of dental patients, as a specific phenomenon in dental practice, should also be investigated. In contemporary medicine, the patient's role is progressively pivotal. If early viewed as a mere object of medical intervention, the patient is now considered an equal partner with the doctor in the treatment process. In this regard, stomatology stands out as the field of medicine where the exclusive features of the patients are most prominent, distinguishing them from other types (therapeutic, surgical and etc.) of patients.

Consequently, on the one hand, the more the doctor of dental medicine is familiar with patient data and the higher their level of awareness is in relation to the patient, the better they will manage the treatment process, making it easier to provide a high level of care.

On the other hand, the more knowledgeable and aware the patient is about the treatments and procedures

performed or upcoming, the more they will view themselves as an equal partner in relationship with attending doctor. As it is becoming increasingly clear, all of this is one of the strongest factors in the process of providing high-level treatment to dental patients.

The Aim of the Study

Based on the above, the aim of the study is to assess the level of knowledge and awareness of patients regarding current and upcoming treatments and procedures in dental clinics in Tbilisi.

Study/Research objectives:

Assessment of preventive activities of patients in Tbilisi dental clinics, specifically evaluating the feasibility of measures attributed to the preventive interventions of oral cavity diseases in these clinics.

► Measuring the level of patients trust in dental services provided or to be provided by the medical (dental) staff in dental clinics.

► Based on the characterization and analysis of the provided information, assess the level of patient awareness about the manipulations and treatments performed and/or planned, that is, the assessment of their knowledge of oral pathologies and the necessary treatment measures and procedures to be carried out in the clinic.

Study Material and Methods:

The study was conducted in non-stationary dental clinics in Tbilisi (New-Dent Ltd, GR Universe Ltd, Bio-Dent Ltd) through an anonymous survey of patients (131) and doctors of dental medicine (119) willing to

participate using the questionnaires prepared preliminary and separately for patients and doctors. The criteria for selecting the research sites were:

1. Priority for conducting research was given to clinics engaged in both curative-prophylactic work and educational and scientific processes. The doctors in these clinics are involved in medical, scientific, and pedagogical activities, which provides them with a broader knowledge base on the issues we are studying, thus facilitating the course of our research to a certain extent.

2. Study participants:

A total of 250 individuals participated in the study, 119 of which were medical personnel (doctors, nurses, assistant doctors) and 131 – patients, respectively. The selection of potential participants took place at the aforementioned dental clinics upon referral. All medical staff and incoming patients meeting inclusion criteria developed by us and at the same time, expressing their desire to cooperate, which is confirmed by signatures on the informed consent, were offered to fill in the questionnaire.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Respondents aged 5 years and above; in cases where the respondent is below 18, informed consent is obtained from a person accompanying the patient (a parent, official guardian, or relative);
2. Respondent is fluent in Georgian;
3. The respondent agrees to independently complete the provided questionnaire (refer to attachment). For pediatric patients, accompanying individuals will fill out the questionnaire on their behalf.

Inclusion Procedures

The willingness of potential study subjects to participate was determined through personal interviews, thereby mitigating any potential pressure that might arise from conducting interviews in the presence of others. Preliminary interviews were conducted in a designated private space to ensure confidentiality. Each participant provided written informed consent to participate in the study, as previously outlined.

Study/Research Instrument

The research instrument comprised original questionnaires developed separately for medical personnel and patients. These questionnaires were distributed to a total of 250 individuals, consisting of 119 medical personnel and 131 patients at the study outset. Prior to distribution, a preliminary piloting of the questionnaire involving 10 patients and 5 dentists was conducted.

Incorporating feedback from the pilot study participants, amendments were made to certain questions and the questionnaire was adapted accordingly. As previously mentioned, the questionnaire was divided into two categories: the first category was intended for completion by the medical staff of the clinics (including doctors of various specialties, nurses, and assistant doctors), while the second category was designed for patients. The questionnaire encompassed questions regarding participants' age, gender, education, referral sources, level of informativeness, and frequency of doctor visits.

Upon completing the survey questionnaires for both medical personnel and patients, the following information was collected:

Patients:

- ▶ Age
- ▶ Gender
- ▶ Education
- ▶ Frequency of dental check-ups.
- ▶ Reasons for dental visits - preventive examination or treatment.
- ▶ Oral health practices.
- ▶ Interest in oral health procedures.
- ▶ Preferred sources of information (written or oral, from the doctor or assistant).
- ▶ The most recent sensitive or invasive procedures undergone.
- ▶ Types of treatments and manipulations received: therapeutic, surgical, orthopedic, orthodontic, and etc.

▶ In addition, the questionnaire tailored for medical personnel incorporates a checklist of essential preventive measures to be implemented. This aspect of the questionnaire facilitated the acquisition of crucial data for analysis, evaluating the execution of preventive interventions in clinics across various patient categories, considering factors such as age, gender, education level, occupation, and so on.

Doctors:

- ▶ Age
- ▶ Gender
- ▶ Education
- ▶ Occupation/position
- ▶ Procedures frequently performed by the doctor.
- ▶ Preventive interventions, envisaging information relayed to patients by the doctor (nurse, assistant).

▶ Details regarding treatment of existing diseases and preventive measures crucial for avoiding specific dental conditions. Additionally the variety of informational media (mass media, printed materials, radio, television, animated films, and other relevant mediums) available at the clinic for providing comprehensive information to patients, particularly children and their families. Therefore, the questionnaire provides an answer.

Research Results and Discussion

As mentioned previously, the study participants were categorized into two groups: medical staff and patients. The age range for patients spanned from 5 to 65 years, with the majority (46.6%) falling within the 5-25 years age group. In the case of medical personnel, the minimum age of the respondents - 18 years and the maximum - 65 years, respectively.

A substantial majority of the interviewed medical personnel were women, constituting 86.6% (109 individuals) of the total respondents, while men represented 13.4% (16 individuals). Among the patient population, women outnumbered men, with 98 (74.8%) females compared to 33 (25.2%) males.

Among the interviewed medical personnel:

- Higher education - 115 (96.6%);
- Secondary education – 4 (3.4%).

Among the interviewed patients:

- Secondary education - 31 (23.7%);
- Higher education 100 (76.3%).

The interviewed medical personnel distributed according to the positions:

- Doctor of Dental Medicine - 84 (70.6%);
- Doctor of Dental Medicine (course of residency) - 1 (0.8%);
- Assistant Doctor of Dental Medicine - 33 (27.7%).
- X-ray Lab. Assistant - 1 (0.8%).

When asked about the frequency of oral health check-ups, the majority of surveyed patients responded as follows:

- Often examined the oral and teeth health status: 47.3%.
- Rarely examined the oral and teeth health status: 45.8%.
- Examined the oral and teeth health status only when necessary (during pain): 6.1%.
- Regarding the question posed to the medical staff about the most frequent treatments or procedures performed, the respondents answered that they are asked to conduct preventive examinations in 7.6% of cases, in the other cases, they conducted medical manipulations (84%) and X-ray examination was used in 8.4%. The above opinion was confirmed by 105 respondents (80.2%) who stated that patients typically seek treatment due to toothache or other problems, while 26 respondents (19.8%) indicated that patients come for the prevention of dental diseases.

To the question posed to the medical staff: "What **preventive** measures are taken for the oral cavity?" the following responses were revealed:

- Everything related to the oral cavity: 11 (9.2%).
- Conversations: 16 (13.4%).
- Preventive examinations: 18 (23.5%).
- Not implemented: 64 (53.8%).

Simultaneously, we asked the patients: "What do you do for your oral health?" The responses were as follows:

- Irregular use of toothpaste and mouthwash: 12.2% (16 individuals).
- Frequent visits to the doctors: 25.2% (33 individuals).
- Brushing teeth in the morning and evening: 44.3% (58 individuals).
- Nothing special: 18.3% (24 individuals).

Based on the research objectives, study contingent (medical staff of dental profile and patients) were asked about patient awareness. Among them:

To the medical staff: "Do you provide patients with information about the dental treatment and procedures to be performed?" The responses were:

- 75.6% of the respondents indicated that they provide patients with proper information about the treatments and procedures to be performed, while 24.4% of the respondents stated that they do not provide this information because the patients do not want to hear it.

Additionally, 93.1% of patient respondents indicated that they are interested in information about the

treatments and procedures performed (or upcoming) and require adequate information. Conversely, 6.9% of the interviewed patients are not interested in the treatments and procedures performed (or upcoming) and, therefore, do not ask for any information about them;

To the question: "From whom do you receive information about the conducted manipulations?" the patients answered as follows:

- 74% (97 respondents) believe that they systematically receive this information from the doctor of dental medicine.
- 26% (34 respondents) believe that they received information independently from the attending doctor.

The patients were also asked: "What procedures did you undergo last?"

It was found that:

Treatment procedures (manipulations) were performed on 71.8% (94) of 131 patients. Preventive examinations were conducted on 28.2% (37), respectively. Also, out of the 131 surveyed patients, 55.7% (73 patients) were offered treatment due to the needs by the doctors, while 44.3% (58 patients) were not offered it.

If we compare the results of our study with data from more or less similar studies conducted in EU countries, we will notice that both the implementation of preventive interventions and the execution of treatment measures significantly exceed the data we have obtained.

In particular, in European countries, both children and adult patients tend to visit a dentist much more frequently, and preventive measures are more commonly implemented among the adult patients. Similar trends are observed regarding preventive measures as well. The frequency of referrals and the structure of diseases according to European data also tend to exceed our findings. This suggests that the prevalence of basic dental diseases is similar between our region and developed countries. However, it's important to note that our patients may not have the same financial security as those in Europe, which could underpin our results. Similar trends are observed in terms of gender, age, and education.

Finally, upon considering the comprehensive analysis of the collected data, several significant conclusions can be drawn.

Conclusions:

The conducted research has led to the following conclusions:

- Currently, in Georgia, there is a low level of patient activity in seeking dental care.
- Also, the level of patient awareness is unfavorable both on the part of doctors (due to inadequate information provision by doctors) and on the part of patients (lack of insistence on receiving such information). Considering the above in a more specific context, it should be noted that the opportunities for clinics to inform a large number of patients using mass media, printed materials, radio, and television are quite limited in Georgia. In contrast, the situation in clinics in European countries is noticeably higher in this regard.

The conducted study revealed the following:

- Patients with higher education levels more frequently seek awareness from medical staff compared to those with lower education levels. In other words, the level of education of the researched individuals is directly proportional to their desire to be timely and adequately informed about the treatment or preventive measures to be carried out for them.

- The study also allowed to conclude that the "doctor-patient" relationship in terms of awareness is still superficial today.

Recommendations:

1. The medical staff of dental clinics should intensify efforts to increase patient awareness about treatment strategies and tactics. They should particularly underline the importance of patients taking responsibility for their oral health.

2. Patients should be encouraged to strictly adhere to prescribed treatments, especially for conditions like gingivitis and periodontitis, where prolonged treatment is necessary. Discontinuation of treatment or preventive measures during these periods can lead to serious consequences.

3. Medical personnel should enhance efforts to promote preventive activities among patients (particularly children and adults). This can be achieved through various promotional events and advertising campaigns promoting a healthy lifestyle. Mass media should be utilized extensively for this purpose.

4. The education of patients and, especially, children and adult patients regarding the routine care of the oral cavity and teeth should be given special importance in the process of working with the mentioned contingent. This education should be a key component of the doctor-patient interaction in dental clinics.

5. Raising the level of awareness of the patient about the treatment-prophylactic measures to be carried out is one of the serious links in the complex of measures, the implementation of which should lead to a serious reduction of dental morbidity in the population.

References

1. Intravital microscopy as a tool to study drug delivery in preclinical studies. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 63:119-28.

2. Announcement: NIDCR Supplement to the Journal of Public Health Dentistry on Behavioral and Social Intervention Research Essentials. 2014;

3. Approved Products - Gardasil. 2014;

4. Arantes R, Santos RV, Frazão P. 2010; Oral health in transition: the case of Indigenous peoples from Brazil. *Int Dental J.* (3S2):235-40.

5. Therapeutic Dentistry Edited by E. Borovsky. 2010. Dental Caries.

6. Therapeutic Dentistry Edited by E. Borovsky. 2010. Changes in oral mucosa